

Forensic Analysis of Conformity & Non-Conformity of Adani Group Based on Benford's Law

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Abstract:

Corporate reporting allows companies to convey their value openly. Such reports are essential for organizations seeking transparency, fairness, and accountability. They enable companies to highlight the financial health of their business. One year after Hindenburg Research made allegations of stock manipulation against the Adani Group, this study is designed to investigate a dataset encompassing the opening and closing stock prices of different companies within the Adani Group. The goal is to detect any instances of non-conformity. Utilizing a widely recognized forensic accounting technique like Benford's Law, verification is carried out using the mean absolute deviation. The database comprises the opening and closing stock prices of six companies within the Adani Group sourced from the National Stock Exchange (NSE). The findings indicate that the stock prices, as reported in the NSE from the day following their listing, deviate from Benford's distribution, and the level of adherence to this distribution diminishes notably. Adani Enterprises Ltd. and Adani Power Ltd. exhibit satisfactory conformity within the second-digit range. This investigation solely addresses the six companies within the Adani Group in response to allegations by Hindenburg Research and OCCRP, excluding examinations of scams or scandals involving other institutions. The study employs a single method, namely MAD, to assess conformity with Benford's Law.

Keywords Forensic accounting, Benford's Law, Mean absolute deviation, Stock manipulation

Introduction:

According to reports, the Indian conglomerate Adani Group was part of a multi-decade-long operation involving widespread accounting fraud and stock manipulation ("Adani Group," 2023). Documents obtained exclusively by OCCRP that are classified as confidential disclose how non-transparent investment funds facilitated the channelling of hundreds of millions of dollars into publicly-traded Adani stock (Arcadio et al., 2023). The stock prices of its seven key listed companies have experienced unexplained surges, with many witnessing significant multifield increases ("Adani Group," 2023). Forensic accounting serves as a crucial link between accounting activities and providing evidential support concerning financial statement fraud, which can be utilized as legal evidence in court proceedings (Choi et al., 2009). Five strategies are used in this approach: Benford's Law, target beating, evaluation of anomalous accruals, investigation of irregularities in post-decimal digits, and use of audit-based predictors (Honigsberg, 2020). The rising occurrences of diverse corporate financial scandals have emphasized the significance of forensic accounting, which offers a spectrum of tools for investigating corporate fraud. These tools not only have the potential to prevent corporate fraud incidents but also serve to mitigate the risk associated with fraud (Akinbowale et al., 2020).

The purpose of this research is to look at the dataset containing the opening and closing stock

prices of various companies within the Adani Group to identify any instances of non-conformity. The focus of this article is on investigating potential "Data Manipulation" in the stock price data of the Adani Group. Mark J. Nigrini's Bedford's Law (Nigrini, 2012) is considered particularly suitable for a thorough analysis of stock price data, providing a comprehensive approach to detecting irregularities. We employ Benford's Law, a widely recognized and praised method in forensic auditing, to evaluate the accuracy of the reported data concerning the opening and closing stock prices of various crucially listed companies within the Adani Group. This empirical research holds significant importance given the prevailing high levels of doubt and scepticism surrounding stock prices.

Adani Group:

The Adani Group, headquartered in Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India, has achieved a dominant position in its transport logistics and energy utility portfolio businesses through strategic market leadership. The company has prioritized extensive infrastructure development on a large scale within India over the years ("About us | Growth with Goodness," n.d.). The principal holdings of the Adani Group in India consist of ten publicly traded entities: NDTV Ltd., Adani Enterprises Ltd., Adani Green Energy Ltd., Adani Energy Solutions Ltd., Adani Total Gas Ltd., Adani Wilmar Ltd., Adani Ports and Special Economic Zone Ltd., and Adani Wilmar Ltd. Adani New Industries Ltd., Adani Solar, Adani Wind, Adani

ConneX, Adani Airport Holdings Ltd., Adani Roads Transports Ltd., Adani Digital Ltd., Real Estate, and Other Specialty Businesses (Defense & Aerospace, Agri Fresh, Integrated Resources Management, Mining services, Copper, Petrochemicals, Water, PVC & Aluminium) are among the companies that are not listed (“Adani Group Brochure August 2023.pdf,” 2023).

Benford's Law:

Benford's rule, also known as the first-digit rule or Newcomb-Benford law, has its origins in an important finding made by Canadian-American astronomer Simon Newcomb in the late 1800s. Newcomb noticed a distinct pattern where the initial entries, particularly those starting with "1," exhibited a significant deviation from the subsequent entries, being notably less frequent (Newcomb, 1881). The law is named after American mathematician and physicist Frank Benford, who originally reported the phenomena in a 1938 article titled "The Law of Anomalous Numbers" (Benford, 1938). In his study, he looked at the first few digits of numbers that came from a variety of places, such as river flow areas, science constants, and population counts. According to the results of his study, the digit "1" was the first to appear 30.6% of

the time, while the digit "2" was first 18.5% of the time.

Formula:

$$P(d) = \text{Log}_{10} \left(1 + \frac{1}{d} \right)$$

Since d is the first digit (1, 2, ..., 9) and Log_{10} is the base-10 logarithm, P(d) is the chance that the first digit will be d. As an example, the likelihood that the initial digits will be 9 is 0.04576 ($\text{log} (1+1/9)$). (see Table I).

$$P(d_1) = \text{Log}_{10} \left(1 + \frac{1}{d_1} \right)$$

Here, d_1 is the first digit (0, 1, 2, ..., 9) and P(d_1) is the probability that the second digit will be d_1 . Log_{10} is the base-10 logarithm. As an example, the likelihood that the first digit will be 9 is 0.08500 ($\text{log} (1+1/9)$). (see Table I).

$$P(dd_1) = \text{Log}_{10} \left(1 + \frac{1}{dd_1} \right)$$

Where dd_1 is the first digit (10, 11, ..., 99), and P(dd_1) is the probability that the first digit will be dd_1 . Log_{10} is the base-10 logarithm. For instance, 0.04252 ($\text{log} (1+1/10)$) is the likelihood that the initial digits will be 10.

Table I Expected Digit Frequencies on Benford's Law

Digit	First Digit	Second Digit
0	-	0.11968
1	0.30103	0.11389
2	0.17609	0.10882
3	0.12494	0.10433
4	0.09691	0.10031
5	0.07918	0.09668
6	0.06695	0.09337
7	0.05799	0.09035
8	0.05115	0.08757
9	0.04576	0.08500

Source: (Nigrini, 1996)

Overall, Benford's Law has found application in identifying irregularities in: (a) Academic Research (Horton et al., 2020), (Alves et al., 2016), (Tošić and Vičić, 2021) (B) Financial Reporting (Žgela and Dobša, 2011), (Alali and Romero, 2013), (Máté et al., 2017) (C) National Economic Statistics (Cerqueti and Maggi, 2021), (Judge and Schechter, 2009), (Michalski and Stoltz, 2013) (D) Investigative Examinations (Badal-Valero et al., 2018), (Lacasa and Fernández-Gracia, 2019), (Figueiredo Filho et al., 2022) (E) Fraudulent Tax activities (Ausloos et al., 2017), (Demir and Javorcik, 2020) and (f) Data Reported During Global Health Crises (Balashov et al., 2021), (Campolieti, 2022), (Mahasuar, 2022).

(Nigrini, 2015) highlights several crucial properties, including the scale-invariance property, signifying its independence from measurement

units. This characteristic renders it a potent tool for testing data across diverse sources, such as different countries and companies (Henselmann et al., 2013).

(Nigrini and Miller, 2007) determined that the conformity to Benford's Law was almost ideal, employing the Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) as the conformity metric. To assess the accuracy of fitted time-series data, MAD is used in time-series analysis. A low degree of error indicates that the fitted time series values are quite near to the actual values, confirming the forecast's dependability (Nigrini, 2011). Table II states that MAD values of conformity to non-conformity.

Formula:

$$\text{Mean absolute deviation} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K |AP - EP|}{K}$$

where K is the number of bins, and the first, second, and first two numbers, 9, 10, and 90,

respectively, denote the anticipated, actual, and perpetual proportions, EP and AP, respectively.

Table II Critical values range for mean absolute deviation

Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD)	First Digit	Second Digit	First- Two digit
Close conformity	0.0-0.006	0.00-0.008	0.0000 to 0.0012
Acceptable conformity	0.006-0.012	0.008-0.010	0.0012 to 0.0018
Marginally acceptable conformity	0.012-0.015	0.010-0.012	0.0018 to 0.0022
Nonconformity	>0.015	>0.012	>0.0022

Source: (Nigrini, 2011)

Literature Review

Hindenburg Research is a unique forensic financial research company that was founded in 2017 by Nathan Anderson and specializes in credit, equities, and derivatives analysis. Hindenburg Research, which is well-known for exposing corporate wrongdoing and taking stances against involved businesses, specializes in comprehensive forensic financial investigation (“About Us – Hindenburg Research,” n.d.). In January 2023, the firm levied serious accusations against the Adani Group, alleging involvement in money laundering, accounting malpractices, and market manipulation (“Adani Group,” 2023). OCCRP also alleged stock manipulation in Adani Group (Arcadio, 2023).

Hindenburg's report raised concerns about offshore entities and posed various questions regarding the Adani Group's financial practices. According to the study, there were allegations that Adani family members were running offshore shell companies in tax havens including Mauritius, the United Arab Emirates, and the Caribbean Islands (Singhania et al., 2020). It further asserted that these entities were allegedly involved in generating false import and export documentation, creating fictitious turnovers, and diverting funds from listed companies (Singh, 2023).

In response to Hindenburg's 413-page report, Adani Group's chairman, Gautam Adani, vehemently denied all allegations, dismissing them as unfounded (“Adani vs Hindenburg,” 2023.). The group characterized the document as a malicious blend of selective misinformation and concealed facts, challenging the integrity of the accusations put forth by Hindenburg Research (“Hindenburg’s allegations vs Adani’s response: Shell companies, money laundering, Vinod Adani’s role - BusinessToday,” 2023.). The Adani Group also rejected OCCRP’s allegations termed as “recycled” (“India’s Adani Group rejects OCCRP report it used ‘opaque’ funds to invest,” 2023).

Adani, a renowned Indian multinational conglomerate founded in 1988 by Gautam Adani, is headquartered in Ahmedabad, Gujarat (“About us | Growth with Goodness,” n.d.). Throughout the years, it has transformed into one of the most

substantial commercial entities in India. It has grown into one of the biggest business organizations in India throughout the years. In addition to coal mining and trading, the Adani Group also operates ports, conducts multimodal logistics, generates and transmits power, distributes gas, manufactures solar PV components, and develops platforms, technologies, systems, and aerostructures for the aerospace and defense industries (“Adani Group Brochure August 2023.pdf,” 2023). With operations spanning across India, Indonesia, Australia, Singapore, Panama, the UAE, and Mauritius, Adani has established a robust presence in various sectors on a global scale.

In our investigation, we use Benford's Law to evaluate a company's possible susceptibility to stock manipulation by taking into account all available data about that corporation. (Aggarwal and Dharni, 2020) show a significant difference among shell companies and legitimate enterprises through first and second-digit analyses using KS statistics and MAD. (Carslaw, 1988) identified a correlation between the manipulation of income by managers in New Zealand companies and an augmentation of the second digit 0 alongside a reduction of the second digit 9. Auditors have explored Benford’s Law as a tool (Durtschi et al., 2004). (Kumar and Bhattacharya, 2007) the primary objective is to evaluate the credibility of a collection of accounting information, specifically as perceived by a financial investigator or auditor. Consequently, if the variables under examination were manipulated in the years leading up to a company's failure to obscure financial difficulties, it is anticipated that these variables would deviate from conformity with the law (Alali and Romero, 2013).

Methodology

The methodology involving anticipated frequencies of digits within a series of numerical value is recognized as Benford's Law (Nigrini, 2011). This section describes the methodology used to investigate the relationship with Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) in the evaluation of compliance with Benford's Law (Cerqueti and Maggi, 2021) and employed to identify uncertainty within the dataset.

Sources of Data

The information for this study was obtained from publicly available sources finance.yahoo.com (Hiransha et al., 2018) from this we accessed ten out of six public listed companies of Adani's group from their historical data. We took only the opening price and closing price denotes the initial trading value of an asset at the beginning of a transaction day in a marketplace (Dutta et al., 2023). Here we have used the day-wise opening price and closing price of six companies of Adani Group from stock markets National Stock Exchange (NSE) of India. The daily

opening price and closing price from the date of listing of each company in the stock markets and some of the historical data couldn't achieved from their listed date but we managed to get it from, for example, Adani Enterprises Limited (ADANIENT.NS) came out with an IPO (Initial Public Offering) on 12th September 1994, and it was listed on NSE in 4th June 1997 but historical data shows from 02-07-2002 so we took from that date for analysis. Table III shows the stock opening price and closing price for each Adani Group company.

Table III Opening and Closing Stock Price of Six Companies of Adani Group

Adani Enterprises Limited (ADANIENT.NS)			Adani Ports and Special Economic Zone Limited (ADANIPTS.NS)		
Date	Opening Price (Rupees)	Closing Price (Rupees)	Date	Opening Price (Rupees)	Closing Price (Rupees)
02-07-2002	1.386372	1.373344	28-11-2007	194	177
03-07-2002	1.371811	1.373344	29-11-2007	181	177.4
04-07-2002	1.379475	1.381008	30-11-2007	178	185.8
05-07-2002	1.388672	1.377942	03-12-2007	187.95	196
08-07-2002	1.394803	1.438486	04-12-2007	197.35	209.8
09-07-2002	1.433121	1.400934	05-12-2007	210	216.8
10-07-2002	1.41013	1.399401	06-12-2007	210.2	218.02
11-07-2002	1.449215	1.37641	07-12-2007	220	220
12-07-2002	1.391737	1.387139	10-12-2007	220.33	214.71
15-07-2002	1.371811	1.358783	11-12-2007	216.21	209.2
...
06-12-2023	3080	2883.95	06-12-2023	1045	1017.95
07-12-2023	2900	2887.15	07-12-2023	1029	1039.65
08-12-2023	2902.7	2822.15	08-12-2023	1048	1022.95
11-12-2023	2837.05	2855.8	11-12-2023	1026.8	1031.9
12-12-2023	2869.1	2857.65	12-12-2023	1037.05	1041.95
13-12-2023	2860	2875.05	13-12-2023	1045	1063.5
14-12-2023	2900.95	2894.05	14-12-2023	1080	1074.7
15-12-2023	2912.05	2991.8	15-12-2023	1079	1078.55
18-12-2023	2993.95	2980.6	18-12-2023	1079	1094.3
19-12-2023	2988.8	2941.25	19-12-2023	1095	1074
Adani Power Limited (ADANIPOWER.NS)			Adani Green Energy Limited (ADANIGREEN.NS)		
Date	Opening Price (Rupees)	Closing Price (Rupees)	Date	Opening Price (Rupees)	Closing Price (Rupees)

21-08-2009	99.9	103.15	19-06-2018	32.7	32.6
24-08-2009	103.9	103.1	20-06-2018	31.5	31
25-08-2009	102.5	102.75	21-06-2018	29.45	29.65
26-08-2009	103	105.1	22-06-2018	28.2	29.45
27-08-2009	104.95	104.75	25-06-2018	30	28.95
28-08-2009	104.9	104.65	26-06-2018	28.8	28.8
31-08-2009	102.75	103.2	27-06-2018	28.3	27.4
01-09-2009	103.25	101	28-06-2018	26.05	26.05
02-09-2009	100.3	101.45	29-06-2018	24.75	26.8
03-09-2009	102	100.1	02-07-2018	27.2	25.2
...
06-12-2023	545	560.45	06-12-2023	1474.5	1563.45
07-12-2023	567.95	562.4	07-12-2023	1580	1624.15
08-12-2023	566	533.8	08-12-2023	1645	1550.3
11-12-2023	535	526.15	11-12-2023	1554.4	1530
12-12-2023	527.65	516.95	12-12-2023	1532.85	1463.9
13-12-2023	519.45	505.7	13-12-2023	1459	1427.7
14-12-2023	508.9	528.95	14-12-2023	1435.95	1508.3
15-12-2023	537	538.85	15-12-2023	1527.65	1526.65
18-12-2023	543.15	539.35	18-12-2023	1518.95	1524.65
19-12-2023	547.5	535.45	19-12-2023	1530.5	1531.8
Adani Total Gas Limited (ATGL.NS)			Adani Wilmar Limited (AWL.NS)		
Date	Opening Price (Rupees)	Closing Price (Rupees)	Date	Opening Price (Rupees)	Closing Price (Rupees)
06-11-2018	77	78.1	09-02-2022	273.65	321.9
07-11-2018	79.4	81.3	10-02-2022	356.7	386.25
09-11-2018	84	79.95	11-02-2022	408.7	381
12-11-2018	79.8	76	14-02-2022	364.2	376.3
13-11-2018	72.5	76.95	15-02-2022	394.7	383.85
14-11-2018	77.05	78.3	16-02-2022	390	377.05
15-11-2018	79	79.4	17-02-2022	382	359.8
16-11-2018	79.4	78.85	18-02-2022	352.6	354.3
19-11-2018	78.45	77.8	21-02-2022	351.9	327.6
20-11-2018	81	80.9	22-02-2022	308.6	314.3
...
06-12-2023	915	1053.3	06-12-2023	387	396.35
07-12-2023	1102	1158.6	07-12-2023	398	395.6
08-12-2023	1230	1156.8	08-12-2023	397.7	377.9
11-12-2023	1179.95	1172.15	11-12-2023	379.75	374.3
12-12-2023	1180	1114.2	12-12-2023	375.85	373.7

13-12-2023	1110	1004.55	13-12-2023	374.8	365.45
14-12-2023	1005	1051.55	14-12-2023	367.75	370.05
15-12-2023	1070	1046.95	15-12-2023	372.9	369.25
18-12-2023	1047	1030.55	18-12-2023	371.9	366.8
19-12-2023	1039.7	1026.25	19-12-2023	367.05	363

Source: Author's Compilation

Results:

In this segment, we will draw conclusions regarding by applying established scientific paradigms, notably Benford's Law. The primary focus of our research is to determine the likelihood of data manipulation within the dataset of Adani Group's companies. Following the previously outlined comprehensive framework, our approach begins with data collection, followed by a series of tests to

assess the compatibility of Benford's Law and related statistical measures within the dataset derived from real-world observations. The information comprises time series data recorded on a daily basis.

Initially, our analysis focused on the leading digit of the opening stock price column for each company. Table IV presents the breakdown of the distribution for each digit.

Table IV Opening Stock price for the first digit place of digit-wise distribution of each company.

Adani Enterprises Limited (ADANIENT.NS)		Adani Ports and Special Economic Zone Limited (ADANIPORTS.NS)	
Digit	Distribution (digit count)	Digit	Distribution (digit count)
1	1493	1	1413
2	679	2	509
3	701	3	947
4	828	4	197
5	407	5	65
6	325	6	170
7	328	7	406
8	238	8	215
9	270	9	36
Adani Power Limited (ADANIPOWER.NS)		Adani Green Energy Limited (ADANIGREEN.NS)	
Digit	Distribution (digit count)	Digit	Distribution (digit count)
1	676	1	492
2	614	2	212
3	877	3	147
4	480	4	163
5	350	5	59
6	238	6	40
7	70	7	28
8	93	8	44
9	137	9	174

Adani Total Gas Limited (ATGL.NS)		Adani Wilmar Limited (AWL.NS)	
Digit	Distribution (digit count)	Digit	Distribution (digit count)
1	631	1	0
2	110	2	6
3	184	3	142
4	4	4	105
5	38	5	55
6	100	6	104
7	36	7	44
8	52	8	4
9	110	9	0

Source: Author's compilation

Second, in Table V we have considered the first digit of the closing stock price column entries of each company.

Table V Closing Stock price for the first digit place of digit-wise distribution of each company.

Adani Enterprises Limited (ADANIENT.NS)		Adani Ports and Special Economic Zone Limited (ADANIPTS.NS)	
Digit	Distribution (digit count)	Digit	Distribution (digit count)
1	1489	1	1412
2	683	2	511
3	699	3	953
4	833	4	191
5	398	5	64
6	327	6	166
7	322	7	418
8	244	8	206
9	271	9	37
Adani Power Limited (ADANIPOWER.NS)		Adani Green Energy Limited (ADANIGREEN.NS)	
Digit	Distribution (digit count)	Digit	Distribution (digit count)
1	669	1	492
2	637	2	210
3	871	3	152
4	467	4	159
5	350	5	59
6	236	6	38
7	73	7	27
8	90	8	53

9	142	9	169
Adani Total Gas Limited (ATGL.NS)		Adani Wilmar Limited (AWL.NS)	
Digit	Distribution (digit count)	Digit	Distribution (digit count)
1	631	1	0
2	110	2	5
3	183	3	151
4	6	4	98
5	36	5	50
6	100	6	116
7	37	7	36
8	44	8	4
9	118	9	0

Source: Author's compilation

Figure 1 demonstrates the first digit of opening stock price contrast the observed and expected probabilities based on Benford's Law, taking into consideration the opening price of each following company of Adani Group.

Source: Author's Compilation

Figure 2 demonstrates the second digit contrast the observed and expected probabilities based on Benford's Law, taking into consideration the opening price of each following company of Adani Group.

Source: Author's Compilation

Figure 3 demonstrates the first-two digit contrast the observed and expected probabilities based on Benford's Law, taking into consideration the opening price of each following company of Adani Group.

Source: Author's Compilation

Figure 4 demonstrates the first digit contrast the observed and expected probabilities based on Benford's Law, taking into consideration the closing price of each following company of Adani Group

Source: Author's Compilation

Figure 5 demonstrates the second digit contrast the observed and expected probabilities based on Benford's Law, taking into consideration the closing price of each following company of Adani Group.

Source: Author's Compilation

Figure 6 demonstrates the first-two digit contrast the observed and expected probabilities based on Benford's Law, taking into consideration the closing price of each following company of Adani Group.

Source: Author’s Compilation

Table VI shows the Mean Absolute Deviation opening stock price values of each company.

Companies	Mean Absolute Deviation Range					
	F.D.	Conclusion	S.D.	Conclusion	F-T. D.	Conclusion
Adani Enterprises Limited	0.0173	Nonconformity	0.0081	Acceptable conformity	0.0029	Nonconformity
Adani Ports and Special Economic Zone Limited	0.0484	Nonconformity	0.0151	Nonconformity	0.0070	Nonconformity
Adani Power Limited	0.0404	Nonconformity	0.0081	Acceptable conformity	0.0063	Nonconformity
Adani Green Energy Limited	0.0369	Nonconformity	0.0210	Nonconformity	0.0063	Nonconformity
Adani Total Gas Limited	0.0603	Nonconformity	0.0348	Nonconformity	0.0080	Nonconformity
Adani Wilmar Limited	0.1227	Nonconformity	0.0141	Nonconformity	0.0135	Nonconformity

Source: Author’s compilation

where, F.D.- first digit, S.D.- second digit, F-T.D.- first-two digit.

Table VII shows the Mean Absolute Deviation closing stock price values of each company.

Companies	Mean Absolute Deviation Range					
	F.D.	Conclusion	S.D.	Conclusion	F-T. D.	Conclusion
Adani Enterprises Limited	0.0173	Nonconformity	0.0087	Acceptable conformity	0.0029	Nonconformity
Adani Ports and Special Economic Zone Limited	0.0489	Nonconformity	0.0160	Nonconformity	0.0070	Nonconformity
Adani Power Limited	0.0401	Nonconformity	0.0093	Acceptable conformity	0.0064	Nonconformity

Adani Green Energy Limited	0.0354	Nonconformity	0.0203	Nonconformity	0.0066	Nonconformity
Adani Total Gas Limited	0.0615	Nonconformity	0.0353	Nonconformity	0.0082	Nonconformity
Adani Wilmar Limited	0.1232	Nonconformity	0.0184	Nonconformity	0.0137	Nonconformity

Source: Author's compilation

where, F.D.- first digit, S.D.- second digit, F-T.D.- first-two digit

An analysis of the adherence to Benford's Law regarding the opening and closing prices of Adani Ports and Special Economic Zone Limited, Adani Total Gas Limited, Adani Green Energy Limited, and Adani Wilmar Limited across all three metrics reveals the following: none of these companies conform to the law. Notably, only two companies, Adani Enterprises Limited and Adani Power Limited, demonstrate acceptable conformity within the second digit range see Table VII. Throughout recent years, the stock prices of diverse Adani-listed companies have encountered noteworthy and somewhat enigmatic upswings, exhibiting varying levels of adherence to Benford's Law across the analyzed metrics. Adani Enterprises, for instance, has witnessed a substantial surge in its stock price from 101% to 1398%, Adani Total Gas has experienced a notable increase from 118% to 2121%, Adani Green Energy has shown significant growth from 4% to 908%, Adani Power has undergone an uptick from 167% to 332%, and Adani Ports has seen its stock price climb from 8% to 98% ("Adani Group," 2023). Overall, the companies in the Adani Group generally exhibit nonconformity across the MAD metrics measured, with some variations in the level of conformity. Adani Enterprises Limited and Adani Power Limited is an exception, showing acceptable conformity in the second digit metric.

Conclusion and Discussion:

This study contributes evidence on the applicability of Benford's principle in a developing economic context, specifically regarding identifying of stock manipulation of six companies of the Adani Group. Additionally, Benford's Law evaluates the effectiveness of stock volumes of legitimate companies (Nigrini, 2015). The study is intrigued by the intriguing issues raised by the availability of prior information regarding the characteristics of companies. This information has the potential to improve our comprehension of the general applicability and validity of Benford's Law, specifically as it pertains to financial data disclosed by companies. Through MAD, the discriminating force of Benford's Law is validated (Mahasuar, 2022). Analyzing first-digit, second-digit, and first-two-digit comparison data provides an interesting

viewpoint on the use of Benford's Law. With the exception of two firms (Adani Enterprises Limited and Adani Power Limited) that show a minor increase in second-digit conformance, there is a notable fall in conformity for both the first and first-two digits when stock manipulation occurs inside corporations. Conversely, the majority of other businesses exhibit nonconformity. It is noteworthy that the ratios of mean MAD values for the first and second digit differ when pooled data is analyzed for stock manipulation as opposed to an annual study (Barney and Schulzke, 2016). These results imply that Benford's Law's classification accuracy is maximized when financial data from many years are combined.

Benford's Law, a widely recognized statistical approach, is effective in uncovering potential fraud or manipulation within financial data, whether it is finely detailed or coarse-grained, provided that the time horizon is sufficiently (Nigrini, 2017). While the findings of this study do not allow for the assignment of blame to any specific entity without concrete evidence, they do serve as motivation for subsequent investigations by the pertinent authorities (Demir and Javorcik, 2020). The anomalies observed in stock price fluctuations and deviations from the expected likelihood plot, as indicated by Benford's Law, warrant further scrutiny by relevant authorities (Morales et al., 2022). Nevertheless, Benford's Law lacks the definitive ability to distinguish between naturally occurring data and manipulated data (Kovalerchuk et al., 2007), (Diekmann and Jann, 2010), (Goodman, 2016). The results of this study underscore the significance of utilizing statistical analysis tools such as Benford's Law to detect data manipulation and prevent potential financial crises. It is imperative for companies to enhance their corporate reporting to boost transparency and accountability, and collaborate with statutory bodies to ensure compliance with relevant rules and standards.

Practical Implications:

Benford's Law, when applied to the examination of the Adani Group and its comparison with allegations of stock manipulation from various organizations, suggests a valuable outcome for the study. This application can enhance the

identification and prevention of fraudulent activities. It is recommended to integrate numerical data conformity, encompassing Benford's principle analyses investigating the auditing methodologies within financial organizations. Employing this law in assessments of disclosure can contribute to improved financial quality. Forensic auditing practitioners and firms can anticipate improved outcomes by furnishing timely and precise reporting on financial results and risk management approaches, thereby enhancing transparency and accountability to stakeholders. It's important to note that while Benford's Law is recognized for its potential to ensure conformity, non-conformity with the law does not necessarily imply misreported or fraudulent data.

Limitations and Future Agenda

Benford's Law offers a distinctive perspective to scrutinize the issues surrounding the Adani Group and the accusations put forth by Hindenburg Research and OCCRP. On the flip side, the present study is based on secondary data and certain limitations need to be acknowledged in the context of this inquiry. Among these, the accessibility and reliability of the data emerge as particularly noteworthy constraints. The accuracy and comprehensiveness of the data employed in the study significantly influence the dependability of the findings. Furthermore, the study's limitations may also encompass the extent of the data under examination. Future researchers may consider these cautions and build upon this investigation by employing more resilient data and analytical methods. Beyond Benford's Law, prospective studies could explore alternative statistical approaches for detecting financial deception. The authors propose that forthcoming research delve into the topic further to arrive at a more conclusive understanding, incorporating any added sign that may emerge over time to mitigate risks.

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